

INCLUDED IN UGC CARE LIST
ISSN 0030 – 5324

Journal of The Oriental Institute

Vol. 68 Nos. 1 – 4

सत्यं शिवं सुन्दरम्

Estd. 1949

Accredited Grade 'A' by NAAC

Oriental Institute

The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda
Vadodara

Editor
Sweta Prajapati

INCLUDED IN UGC CARE LIST
ISSN 0030 – 5324

JOURNAL OF THE ORIENTAL INSTITUTE

Issue No. 68, Year 2019

Editor :

Dr. Sweta Prajapati

Accredited Grade 'A' by NAAC

Oriental Institute

The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda
Vadodara

JOURNAL OF THE ORIENTAL INSTITUTE

(Referred and Blind 'Peer-reviewed' Annual International Indological Research Journal)

Vol. 68, Nos. 1-4, September-December 2018 and March-June 2019

© Oriental Institute, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara

Advisory Board :

Prof. Shrinivas Varkhedi

Vice-Chancellor, Kavikulguru Kalidas Sanskrit University, Ramtek, Nagpur

Prof. Gopabandhu Mishra

Vice-Chancellor, Shree Somanath Sanskrit University, Veraval, Gujarat

Prof. N. C. Panda

ICCR Chair Visiting Professor of Sanskrit, Sanskrit Studies Centre, Silpakorn University, Bangkok, Thailand

Prof. Rabindra Kumar Panda

Department of Sanskrit, Pali & Prakrit, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara

Editorial Board :

Dr. Ramanath Pandey

Dr. Sharmila Bagchi

Dr. Vipul Patel

Shri Nandkishor Mishra

Note : *The statements and views expressed by the authors of articles in this Journal are their own and not necessarily of the Editorial Board.*

ISSN	: 0030-5324, INCLUDED IN UGC CARE LIST
Registration No.	: 15007/57
Published by	: Oriental Institute The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda Vadodara - 390 001
Price	: ₹ 150/- Annual subscription (For India) \$ 50 Annual subscription (For Foreign Countries)
Address	: The Director, Oriental Institute The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda Near Palace Gate, Palace Road Vadodara - 390 001, Gujarat, India
Telephone	: (+91-265) 2425121
E-mail	: director-oriental@msubaroda.ac.in
Website	: www.msubaroda.ac.in

CONTENTS

1. *Bhāsvatī* of Śatānanda: In the Pages of *Mystery* - Sudhira Panda 1-17
2. *The Śaiva Āgama*-s and the Fundamental *Śaiva* concepts - T. Ganesan 19-26
3. The Changing Matter and the Unchanging Material Cause: A Study of *Paramatabhaṅga* of Vedānta Deśika - S. Bhuvaneshwari 27-40
4. Ecological Thoughts Exhibited in *Upaniṣads* - Niranjana Jena 41-58
5. Viśvanātha Kavirāja : The Playwright and Poet - Satya Vrat Varma 59-67
6. Vedic Institutions of Medieval and Modern Kerala - Anil Narayanan 69-86
7. The Importance of Plants in Hindu-life - N. C. Kar 87-100
8. Some Female Proper Names in Early *Brāhmī* Inscriptions - Kanika Gupta 101-116
9. A Critical Evaluation of *Līlāvātīvīthi* of Rāmapāñivāda Sugyan Kumar Mahanty 117-156
10. The Prevalance of *Advaita* in Modern Indian Philosophy: Conditioned by the Colonial Era - Kush P. Depala 157-173
11. Contribution of Shri C. D. Dalal to Manuscript Studies - Sweta Prajapati 175-189
12. Contribution of Benoytosh Bhattacharyya to the Fields of Oriental Studies, Buddhist Studies and *Tantra* - Sharmila Bagchi 191-204
13. An Edition of *Samāsacandrikā* of an Anonymous Author - Rabindra Kumar Panda 205-210
14. **सिद्धसिद्धिब्यापातविचारः** : An Unpublished *Nyāya* Text - Vipul Patel 211-214
- Book-Reviews 215-222
- New Arrivals 223-224
- Acknowledgements 225
- Activities of Oriental Institute (2018 - 2019) 227-233

A CRITICAL EVALUATION OF *LĪLĀVATĪVĪTHĪ* OF RĀMAPĀNIVĀDA

Sugyan Kumar Mahanty*

Prologue

Poets write according to their insight which inspires and pleases people. The journey of poet's imagination has started since time immemorial. Classical Sanskrit literature in to two parts - *dr̥śyakāvya* and *śravyakāvya*.¹ *Dr̥śyakāvya*² means drama or play that can be enacted has a visual aspect too. *Dr̥śyakāvya* is also known as *rūpaka*, that is of ten types.³ such as नाटक, प्रकरण, भाण, व्यायोग, समवकार, डिम, ईहामृग, अङ्क, वीथी and प्रहसन.

Bharata, the author of *Nāṭyaśāstra*, defines *vīthī*⁴ as it should have a single act in which one or two characters appear. They may be of noble, middle or low type. It should have all the nine *rasas* and thirty six *Nāṭyalakṣaṇas*. *Vīthī* has thirteen *aṅgas* or constituents, as such; 1. उद्घात्यकम्

Journal of the Oriental Institute, ISSN 0030-5324, Included in UGC Care List, Vol. 68, Nos. 1-4, September-December 2018 and March-June 2019 Issue, pp. 117-156.

* Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, (Deemed University), Vedavyas Campus, Balahar, Dist. Kangra (H.P.)-177108. M : 9625627362, Email: sugyan2003@yahoo.co.in

1. दृश्यश्रव्यत्वभेदेन पुनः काव्यं द्विधा मतम्, साहित्यदर्पणः । 6/1
2. दृश्यं तत्राभिनेयं तद्रूपारोपातुरूपकम् । *Ibid.*
3. नाटकमथ प्रकरणं भाणव्यायोगसमवकारडिमाः ।
ईहामृगाङ्कवीथ्यः प्रहसनमिति रूपकाणि दश ॥ साहित्यदर्पणः, 6/3.
4. वीथी स्यादेकाङ्का तथैकहार्या द्विहार्या वा ।
अघमोत्तममध्याभिर्युक्ताः स्यात्प्रकृतिभिस्तिसृभिः ॥
सर्वरसलक्षणाढ्या युक्ता ह्यङ्गैस्त्रयोदशभिः ।
उद्घात्यकावलगितावस्यन्दितनाल्यसत्प्रलापाश्च ॥
वाक्केल्यथ प्रपञ्चो मृदवाधिवलं छलं त्रिगतम् ।
व्याहारो गण्डश्च त्रयोदशान्यङ्गान्युदाहृतान्यस्याः ॥ *Nāṭyaśāstram*, 18/164-167. Kāvya-mālā Edition,
Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, 1983

(accidental interpretation), 2. अवलगितम् (transference), 3. अवस्यन्दितम् (transferred significance), 4. नालिका (enigmatic expression), 5. असत्प्रलापः (useless talk), 6. वाक्केलिः (repartee). 7. प्रपञ्चः (exaggeration). 8. मृदवम् (softening). 9. अधिवलम् (strengthening argument). 10. छलम् (misinterpretation). 11. त्रिगतम् (tripled or manifold). 12. व्याहारः (talk). 13. गण्डम् (junction or knot).

Dhanañjaya defines *vīthī*⁵ as it should be composed with *kaiśikī vṛtti*. *Sandhyaṅgas* (ancillaries) and *aṅkas* in *vīthī* are like that of *Bhāṇa*, that means there should be one *aṅka* (act) and two *sandhis* (junctures) named *mukha* and *nirvahaṇa* with all its constituent parts or *Sandhyaṅgas* (ancillaries). The *śṛṅgararasa* should be employed predominantly and other *rasas* subordinately.

Unlike other forms of dramatic compositions in Sanskrit, a meager account of *Vīthī* literature is identified, such as *Bakulavīthī*, *Indulekha*, *Mālatikā*, *Mādhavavīthikā* or *Mādhavī Vīthī*, *Kāmadattā*, *Premābhirāma*, *Sītākalyāṇavīthī*, *Candrikā* and *Līlāvātī*, out of which a few specimens are available.

The *Līlāvātīvīthī* and its Author Rāmapāṇivāda

The present Title '*Līlāvātī*'; a *vīthī* is the *magnum opus* of Rāmapāṇivāda, a versatile poet of 18th Century AD, belonged to Kerala, the southern part of India. '*Līlāvātī*'; is a best of the available types of *vīthī* literature in the history of Sanskrit Drama.

i. Life of Rāmapāṇivāda

Rāmapāṇivāda was a great scholar and poet who flourished in Kerala in 18th Century AD and adorned the courts of many of the kings and

5. वीथी तु कैशिकीवृत्ती सन्ध्यङ्गाङ्कैस्तु भाणवत् ।

रसः सूच्यस्तु शृङ्गारः स्पृशेदपि रसान्तरम् ॥

युक्ता प्रस्तावनख्यातैरङ्गैरुद्धात्यकादिभिः ।

एवं वीथी विधातव्या द्वेकपात्रप्रयोजिता ॥ *Daśarūpakam*, 3/68-69.

chieftains of the land at that time. He has been mentioned in a commentary of *Mukundaśatakam*, a *Stotrakāvya* by one of his classmates as-

श्रीमुकुन्दचरणाम्बुजभक्तिभारनिर्निद्रनिर्मलमनोमणिदर्पणस्य ।

रामाहस्य सुकवेर्वदनादुदीर्णं मुख्यं मुकुन्दशतकं जयतीह लोके ॥

सतीर्थ्यतामात्रनिरूढगर्वसम्भावितैतत्कविसाहृदय्यः ।

स्तोत्रं तदीयं विवृणोमि मोहात् सन्तः क्षमन्तां मतिचापलं मे ॥

इह खलु सकलविद्वज्जनगौलिमाणिक्यभूतश्रीनारायणभट्टपादपादारविन्दयुगलपांसुपटलीमरीमृज्यमान-
मतिमयमणिदर्पणप्रतिबिम्बिताशेषागमनिगमसार्धपरमार्थसारः मार्दङ्गिकवंशीमुक्तामणिः रामनामा कविः १६

From the above extracts it is well known that Rāma was his name and Pāṇivāda was the name of his dynasty or the race and he is the disciple of a great scholar and poet of his dynasty or the race and he is the disciple of a great scholar and poet of his time Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa, the author of *Nārāyaṇīya*, *Prakriyāsarvasva*, *Mānameyodaya* and a number of treatises of different genres. Rāmapāṇivāda has to his credit several works of outstanding merit covering almost all branches of Sanskrit literature.

ii. Works of Rāmapāṇivāda

Rāmapāṇivāda was a resourceful and multitalented writer of almost all the genres of creative compositions. The works of Rāmapāṇivāda are :

1. राघवीयम् written under the patronage of the king of Ampalappulā, is another most important treatise in Sanskrit poetic compositions other than *Līlāvati*. राघवीयम् contains 1572 verses in twenty cantos describing the story of the *Rāmāyaṇa* (excluding the *Uttarakāṇḍa*). A few verses dedicating the poem to the king of Ampalappulā are found in a manuscript of the poem. The poem is written in an easy and elegant style, and the poet himself says that it is intended to serve as a textbook for students. The author follows the classical style and conventions, but he is at the same time quite independent and original in his presentation.

6. In the beginning of a commentary of *मुकुन्दशतकम्*, made by a classmate of Rāmapāṇivāda.

2. बालपाठ्यम् is a commentary to his *Mahākāvya* राघवीयम् written by the author himself.
3. विष्णुविलासम् is a *Mahākāvya* was written by him under the patronage of the Paliyat Accan named Rāmakubera, a wealthy chieftain of Chennamagalam.
4. सीताराघवम् is a drama was written by him when he was enjoying the patronage of King Mārtaṇḍavarmā, the maker of Travancore.
5. लीलावती वीथी was composed by him at the request of King Devanārāyaṇa of Amapalappula.
6. चन्द्रिका वीथी was written at the instance of King Virarāya of Vettatunada.
7. मुकुन्दशतकम्, a *Stotrakāvya* was written under the patronage of Ārya Śrīkaṇṭha Rāmavarmā, identified with a member of the Manakkulam family of Kuṇṇamkulam.
8. शिवशतकम्, a *Stotrakāvya*.
9. सूर्यशतकम्, a *Stotrakāvya*.
10. अम्बरनादीशस्तोत्रम्, a *Stotrakāvya*.
11. भागवतचम्पू, a *Campu kāvya*.
12. वृत्तवार्तिकम्, a treatise on metres.
13. तलप्रस्थरकाव्यम्, a short poetry.
14. रसक्रीडा, a short poetry.
15. Two commentaries called विलासिनी and विवरणम् on the *Kṛṣṇavilāsa* authored by Sukumāra.
16. कंसवहो a *Kāvya* in Prakrit Language. The *Kaṃsavaho* describes in four cantos the story of the *Bhāgavata* from Akrura's visit to the death of Kaṃsa.

17. उषानिरुद्ध a *Kāvya* in Prakrit Language. The *Uṣāniruddha* is also based on the story of *Bhāgavatam*. It deals with the episode between Uṣā, the daughter of Bāṇāsura and Aniruddha, grandson of Kṛṣṇa, in four cantos.
18. A commentary on the *Prākṛtaprakāśa* of Vararuci.
19. सारिकासन्देशः - a दूतकाव्यम्.

Besides these, two plays, *Lalitarāghava* and *Pādukapaṭṭābhīṣeka*, and a commentary of *Līlāśuka's Govindābhīṣeka* are also attributed to Rāmapāṇivāda. The Musical poem *Gītārāma* attributed to him by some scholars. Other Sanskrit works attributed to him are *Pancapadi*, a musical poem praising the deity at *Mukkola* temple. *Śṛṅgāravimśati* which is a collection of twenty erotic verses and a work on astrology. Thus the versatile genius Rāmapāṇivāda put his hand in almost all branches of literature, i.e. *Mahākāvyas*, *Nāṭakas*, *Vīthī*, *Stotrakāvyas*, *Campukāvyas*, *Prosody*, *Dūtakāvyas*. Grammar, along with some valuable commentaries also became successful. He was a genuine poet and had mastery over both Sanskrit and *Prākṛta* languages.

Thus it is quite clear from Rāmapāṇivāda's own works that he was a great favorite with kings and chieftains of the land. As the term '*pāṇivāda*' indicates, Rāmapāṇivāda belonged to the class of people called *pāṇivāda* or the Nāmbiār community, whose profession is to help the *Cākyārs* in staging of Sanskrit dramas by playing on the drums called *Milavu* and *Mṛdaṅga*. Rāma was his personal name and *pāṇivāda* an epithet according to the community or class he belonged to as we have discussed above. Rāmapāṇivāda was the pupil of a great scholar of his time named Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa who is mentioned respectfully in the colophons of most of his works.

Some scholars identify Rāmapāṇivāda with the well known Malayalam poet Kuncan Nāmbiār. Ullur S. Paramesvara Iyer, M.R. Balakrishna Varier, Dr. A.N. Upadhyaya and Dr. L.A. Ravivarma are in favour of this identification. But others like Dr. K. Godavarma, Dr. C. Kunjan Raj, Dr. P. K. Narayana Pilla and Vatakkumar Rajarajvarma Raja are against with such identification.

Both Rāmapāṇivāda and Nāmbiār belonged to same Nāmbiār community, and both of them flourished in the courts of the Kings of *Ampalappula* and *Travancore*. The personal name of Kuncan Nāmbiār is not known. Kuncan is the popular pet name of the Malayalam poet moreover, both seem to have been members of the same family. Kuncan Nāmbiār belonged to *Kalakkattu* house in the village of *Killikkurissimangalan*, near the present *Lakkidi* Railway Station, and Rāmapāṇivāda has stated that he himself belonged to the village *Mangalagrāma*. Though there is also *Mangalagrāma* in *Vettatunada*, the one referred to be Rāmapāṇivāda could be identical with *Killikkurissimangalam* itself. But the fact that both poets belonged to the same house and were almost contemporaries need not necessarily prove that they are identical.

Rāmapāṇivāda mentions his guru Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa in almost all his genuine works, and the colophons of the works attributed to Rāmapāṇivāda. But Kuncan Nāmbiār, author of the Tullal works in Malayalam, does not refer to Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa in any of his works. On the other hand, he mentions his teachers differently; Dronappilli Potti and Nadikkara Balaravi Kurup, neither of whom is referred to by Rāmapāṇivāda.

iii. Time of Rāmapāṇivāda

The style of both, Rāmapāṇivāda and Kuncan Nāmbiār are different. Rāmapāṇivāda's style is chaste and lucid, where as the style of Kuncan Nāmbiār which is rather indiferent in grammar, boisterously witty and full of topical anachronisms. It is already said that Rāmapāṇivāda was patronized by the King of *Vettatunada*, the chieftain Paliyath Accan, the King of *Ampalappula*. King Āryā Śrikāntha Ravivarman of Manakkulam, and King Martṭaṇḍavarman of Travancore. Only two of these find mention in the Malayalam works of Kuncan Nāmbiār, namely, the Kings of *Ampalappula* and Travancore. The two Malayalam works *Śivapurāṇa* and *Ekādaśimahātmya* generally attributed to Kuncan Nāmbiār were written under the patronage if the chieftain of *Manakkol*. Accan named Balarāma who flourished only till 1740 A.D. Hence these two works must be assigned to a date earlier than 1740 A.D. There were two Rāmas and one Kṛṣṇa.

In Kalakkattu family at that time the great Sanskrit scholar. Rāmapāṇivāda had a younger brother named Kṛṣṇa and a nephew named Rāma. In the Tullal work *Ghosayātra* Kuncan Nāmbiār *Līlāvātīvīthī*, and annotates it at length : this suggests that he was a younger contemporary of Rāmapāṇivāda. There are references to Kuncan Nāmbiār in the administrative records of Travancore beginning from 1744 A.D. to 1754 A.D. that he must have been patronized by Mārṭṭaṇḍavarman and his successor Kārtika Tirunal Rāmavarman. And there are many Tullal works of Kuncan Nāmbiār, where Kārtika Tirunal Rāmavarman is praised. But in none of the works of Rāmapāṇivāda any reference to this king is found. This also suggests that Rāmapāṇivāda must have been preceded to Kuncan Nāmbiār or an elder contemporary of Kuncan Nāmbiār.

iv. Introduction to *Līlāvātīvīthī* :

The *Līlāvātī* of Rāmapāṇivāda is a type of drama categorized as *vīthī*. The *Līlāvātīvīthī* is considered to be one of the best of very few known representatives of this kind. Another *vīthī* by name *Candrikā* is attributed to the same author, in which he gives the characteristics of this type drama in the verse :

पादद्वयप्रयोज्या भाणवदेकाङ्किका द्विसन्धिश्च ।

आकाशभाषितवती कृत्रिममितिवृत्तमाश्रिता वीथी ॥

Meaning - a *vīthī* is an one-act drama with an artificial plot, having two characters, two junctures (*mukha* and *nirvaḥaṇa*) and abundant in *ākāśabhāṣitas*. The *Daśarūpaka* assigns two more characteristics to this type of dramatic composition, namely the *kaiśikivṛtti* and *śṅgārarasa*; as it reads :

वीथी तु कैशिकीवृत्तौ सन्ध्यङ्गाङ्कैस्तु भाणवत् ।

रसः सूच्यस्तु शृङ्गारः स्पृशेदपि रसान्तरम् ॥⁷

The *Līlāvātī* is a specimen to reflect all these characteristics of a *vīthī*.

7. *Daśarūpaka*, III. 62.

iv. (i-a) Recession and Edition of *Līlāvātīvīthī*

Only one edition of *Līlāvātīvīthī* is found that is based on a copy published by The University Manuscripts Library, University of Travancore, Trivandrum, Printed by the Superintendent Government Press in 1948, that had been developed from Ms. No. 958A of the Curator's collections in this Library, legibly written in Malayalam script, procured from Narayanan Elayathu, Vempanattillam, Ampalapuzha, N. Travancore. Some typographical mistakes were found in the copy published by The University Manuscripts Library, University of Travancore, Trivandrum and corrected in this edition.

iv. (i-b) The Plot of *Līlāvati*

The King of *Karnāṭa* places his beloved daughter *Līlāvati* under the care of *Kalāvati*, the wife of King *Vīrapāla* of *Kuntala* out of fear of the abduction by his enemies, *Vīrapāla*'s love for *Līlāvati* is explicitly revealed in the enthusiastic enquiry about her. He asks *vidūṣaka* :

अपि खलु कुशलं मे नेत्रयोरायतानामपि च जघनभारे दूरविस्तारभाजाम् ।
कुचसरसिजयुग्मे चोन्नतानां घनानां दशनवसनबिम्बे चारुणानामसूनाम् ॥⁸

In spite of *Kalāvati* keeps her out of the sight of the King *Vīrapāla* fearing the possibility of the development of a love affair between them; they, however, happen to meet and fall in love with each other. *Vaiḥāsika*, the boon companion of the king, comes to know of this and arranges with a *Yoginī* by name *Siddhimatī* to bring about their union by magical means. *Līlāvati* is also unable to bear the separation from *Vīrapāla*.

Describing *Kalāvati*'s angry mood. *Vīrapāla* concerns and justifies her anger about his love affair. Her angry mood is always present before his eyes, as he says :

8. *Līlāvati*, 22.

किमपि चपलं जानत्या मे सुखेन सखीमुखा-
 दरुणिमगुणो देव्या नाद्यापि मुञ्चति लोचने ।
 कुचकलशयोः कोपोदीर्णो न शाम्यति बेपथु-
 र्गलतलगलद्वाष्पो रुन्धेतरां परुषाक्षरम् ॥⁹

His condition as he is torn between the love for two women is very well brought out by himself :

कालोऽयं खलु नीलकण्ठनटनाटोपप्रियं भावुकः
 पान्थान्तःस्मयपश्यतोहरतटिद्वल्लीसुखाकारकः ।
 देवी च प्रणयानुरोधविमुखी लीलावती चेदृशी
 कामो वामतरो विधिश्च विषमो हा हन्त का मे गतिः ॥¹⁰

His love for the queen is equally strong. Knowing that the queen is bitten by the serpent, he being unable to bear the intensity of the calamity; faints immediately. And after getting up he feels useless to live without her.

दष्टा चेदणकभुजङ्गमेन देवी
 कष्टं भो विफलमिदं हि जीवितं मे ।
 कर्णाटक्षितिपतिकन्यकानुरक्तं
 हे चेतो जहिहि शतं मनोरथानाम् ॥¹¹

When the queen is revived, he heaves a sigh of relief and says :

यत्ते बालशिरीषनूतनदलस्पर्धालु मुग्धं वपुः
 कष्टं दष्टमभूत्करालगरलज्वालेन कालाहिना ।
 तेनानेन जनेन सुन्दरि ! चिरं मूर्च्छायितं सांप्रतं
 शान्ते तत्र विषोष्मणि श्वसितमित्येतन्महत्कौतुकम् ॥¹²

9. *Ibid*, 25.

10. *Ibid*, 31.

11. *Ibid*, 39.

12. *Ibid*, 44.

आशीर्वचनसंयुक्ता स्तुतिर्यस्मात्प्रयुज्यते ।
देवद्विजनृपादीनां तस्मान्नान्दीति संज्ञिता ॥

मङ्गल्यशङ्खचन्द्राब्जकोककैरवशंसिनी ।
पदैर्युक्ता द्वादशभिरष्टाभिर्वा पदैरुत ॥¹⁴

तत्पादपद्मयुगलं गिरिकन्यकाया
लोकातिशायिचरितं भवतः पुनातु ।
उल्लासयन्ति यदिदं मुहुरीश्वरस्य
चूडानिशाकरकिशोरमयूखलेखाः ॥¹⁵

“May the two lotus like feet, of Gaurī, that possess the glory surpassing the entire world; gladdened by the streaks of rays of the crescent moon existing on the head of the lord Śiva; protect you”.

Here the poet performs The *nāndī* with an invocation to Lord Śiva and Goddess Gaurī in a conventional way, with the words, like *padma niśākara* etc. indicative of good fortune. This *nāndī* is *dvādaśapādī* having twelve words.

The *nāndī* not only provides the purpose of benediction, but also makes an indirect reference to some of the incidents of the play. The term *lokātiśayicaritam* indirectly refers to the dream sequence in the play and the reference to Lord Śiva's indicates his appearance in the dream of the queen.

b. The Prologue / प्रस्तावना : After *Nāndī* is performed *Sātradhāra* himself or with his female counterpart *Naṭī* introduces the plot, the character or the theme in the Prologue or *Prastāvanā*. *Sāhityadarpaṇa* reads as :

14. *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 6/24-25

15. *Līlāvātī*, 1

नटो विदूषको वापि पारिपार्श्विक एव वा ।

सूत्रधारेण सहिता संलापं यत्र कुर्वते ॥

चित्रैर्वाक्यैः स्वकार्योत्थैः प्रस्तुताक्षेपिभिर्मिथः ।

आमुखं तत्तु विज्ञेयं नाम्ना प्रस्तावनापि सा ॥¹⁶

In the prologue, the *Sūtradhāra* enters and says that he has been ordered by the assemblage to present a play. The members of the assemblage are beholden to King Devanārāyaṇa whose heart is always engrossed in analysing the intricacies of all the scriptures, the mythology, the dramas and other forms of literature.

Sūtradhāra is ordered to act a play that is intended to be a *vīthī* which evokes simple and sweet rasas and which consists of wonderful episodes. It should be composed in a noble style with vivid expressions.¹⁷ The *Sūtradhāra* then asks *Naṭī*, to render music. He says that he has become a little nervous before the assembly consisting of scholars who are steeped in the dramatic art and who have dived deep into the various art forms. In the course of the conversation, the *Sūtradhāra* reveals that he is going to present a play called *Līlāvātīvīthī*, composed by Rāmapānīvāda, a nephew of Rāghava Pānīvāda and a resident of Maṅgalagrāma. The attainments of the poet are set forth in a verse form wherein the poet pays his tributes to King Devanārāyaṇa once again.

नित्यं नृत्यति यस्य नाम रसनारङ्गे स्वयं भारती

चित्ते यस्य च भासते सुरधुनीनाथो रथाङ्गायुधः ।

यं भूयो बहुमन्यते नरपतिः श्रीदेवनारायणः

सोऽयं मे हृदये चकास्तु सततं भूदेवचूडामणि ॥¹⁸

Then *Naṭī*, being asked by the *Sūtradhāra* sings a song on the rainy season. He appreciates her for the song. She then poses a question "Sir,

16. *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 6/31-32.

17. अभिनवपदबन्धबन्धुरार्थामभिनय कामपि वीथिकामुदाराम् ।

शुचिरसमधुराणि या बिभर्ति प्रचुरविचित्रतराणि चेष्टितानि ॥ लीलावती/२ ॥

18. *Ibid*, 5.

my sister Raṅgamallikā by name, has a daughter who has fallen in love with a dancer Saṅgītamalla by name. But his first wife by name Raṅgamālā who is filled with jealousy objects to it. Now, may I ask the *brāhmaṇas* assembled here to suggest a way out, by which they could be united?" The narration has a veiled reference to the main story where the heroine falls in love with the king who is already married. The queen is naturally overcome with jealousy when she comes to know of her husband's love affair. Asking the *brāhmaṇas* for help points to the king seeking help from the *vidūṣaka* who is also a *brāhmaṇa*.

Here in this *Prastāvanā* the love of Raṅgamallikā with a dancer Saṅgītamalla having another wife Raṅgamālā indicates the main story where the heroine Līlāvati falls in love with the king Vīrapāla who is already married, for which this is an *Avalagita* type of *Prastāvanā*; As the *Nāṭyaśāstra* reads :

यत्रान्यस्मिन् समावेश्य कार्यमन्यत् प्रसाध्यते ।
तच्चावलगितं नाम विज्ञेयं नाट्ययोक्तृभिः ॥¹⁹

Thus, the prologue has many significant points and it kindles the interest of the audience as well as induces them towards delighting in the play.

c. **Arthopakṣepaka - Viṣkambhaka** : As we know, a play should have one action that it follows, with minimal subplots. To execute the action of the plot in a play in the time limit, to compress the plot geographically and to represent the whole action in a fixed place, a dramatic technique termed as '*Arthopakṣepaka*' has been outlined in the Indian Dramaturgy. So, *Arthopakṣepaka* is a technique by which some of the incidents that need not be / cannot be represented on the stage, are made known to audience. *Sāhityadarpaṇa* defines *Arthopakṣepaka* as under :

19. नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 18. 116

अङ्गेष्वदर्शनीया या वक्तव्यैव च सम्मता ।
 या च स्याद्वर्षपर्यन्तं कथा दिनद्वयादिजा ॥
 अन्या च विस्तरा सूच्या सार्थोपक्षेपकैर्बुधैः ।²⁰

Arthopakṣepaka is said to be of five types, *Viṣkambhaka*, *praveśaka*, *cūlikā*, *anḱāvatāra* and *anḱamukha*. As it is mentioned :

अर्थोपक्षेपकाः पञ्च विष्कम्भकप्रवेशकौ ।
 चूलिकाङ्काऽवतारोऽथ स्यादङ्कमुखमित्यपि ॥²¹

In the beginning of the play, we have *viṣkambhaka*. In the *viṣkambhaka* here, there is a soliloquy by the *vidūṣaka* in which he states that the king had fallen in love with Līlāvati who is guarded by the queen out of jealousy. *Vidūṣaka* also vows to liberate her from the clutches of the queen and unite her with the king. In this endeavour, he would seek the help of the *yoginī*. He sees that Līlāvati's friend Kelimālā is coming in that direction and he indulges in a conversation with her in the form of *ākāśabhāṣita*. The previous history of Līlāvati and her present state are revealed through the conversation. After the *viṣkambhaka* is over, the king enters reciting a verse explaining his love-lorn condition.

In the western dramaturgy '*Arthopakṣepaka*' has been termed as three unities. Aristotle crafted three unities or rules for how to make a perfect tragedy. These unities were, the unity of action, time and place.

- i. **The Unity of Action** : a play should have one action that it follows, with minimal subplots.
- ii. **The Unity of Time** : the action in a play should occur over a period of no more than 24 hours.

20. *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 6/51-52

21. *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 6/54

iii. **The Unity of Place** : a play should exist in a single physical space and should not attempt to compress the geography, nor should the stage represent more than one place.

a) *Bharatavākya*

The conventional *Bharatakāvya* appearing at the end of the play has many noteworthy points.

काव्ये नव्यपुराणभेदगणनाहीना धियो धीमतां
 सद्गृह्णन्तु गुणानणूनपि तथा दोषानपाकुर्वताम् ।
 लोकानामवधूतमत्सरकथामैत्री तथोज्ज्वभतां
 भक्तिर्नक्षिरमेधतां गुरुपदाम्भोजे जगन्मङ्गले ॥²²

May the intellect of the great who are averse to the distinction between the old literature and the new one, appreciate even an iota of merits in the *kāvya* and set aside the demerits. Let amity surpass jealousy in the world. Let the devotion to the lotus feet of the preceptors grow for welfare of the world.

The verse which is secular in nature is quite significant, since it indirectly refers to the joy expressed by the king, his beloved *Lilāvati* and the queen as the latter let off her jealousy and united the two lovers, *Virapāla* and *Lilāvati*.

b) *Vīthyaṅgas*

A *vīthi* is supposed to incorporate its *aṅgas*, that are 13 in number as mentioned above. The *Lilāvativīthi* has all its 13 *aṅgas*. These *Vīthyaṅgas* are essential parts of a *vīthi*, which contribute to design its form as well as accomplish poetic beauty.

22. *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 6/62

1. उद्घात्यकम् (accidental interpretation) :

Udghātyakam (accidental interpretation) is where additional words are used to bring out the meaning of a given sentence which is obscure in its present form.²³

Vidūṣaka makes a statement “अहव दुद्धसाअरं उज्झिय कुदो लच्छी उगच्छद । ता स्रवं विठ्ठदु । (अथवा दुग्धसागरमुज्झित्वा । कुतो लक्ष्मीरुद्रच्छति । तत् सर्वं तिष्ठतु ।)”²⁴, that is obscure in its nature, that needs further reference to bring out its meaning. Later this statement becomes meaningful with the further reference made by *ākāśabhāṣitam*. किं भणसि-‘बेहासिअ! को उण दे कवडणाडअं ण जाणादि’ ति । (किं भणसि? वैहासिक ! कः पुनस्ते कपटनाटकं न जानातीति ।) etc.

2. अवलगितम् (transference) :

*Avalagita*²⁵ is transference of idea to bring out desired effect. The *vidūṣaka* loses the love letter and the signet ear ring. But it is recovered by the queen’s maid. She taunts the *vidūṣaka* by saying that it must have fallen from the ear of the presiding deity of the garden. Here we have an instance of *avalagita* :

(नेपथ्ये)

एत्थ उज्जाणे वम्पीअरन्धमुहट्टिअं सप्पणिम्मोअं विअ घणपण्णुरं एदं दन्तताडङ्कं मए गृहीदं । मण्णे उज्जाणळच्छीए सवणपासादो पब्भट्ठं नि । {अत्रोद्याने बल्मीकरन्ध्रमुखस्थितं सर्पनिर्मोकमिव घनपाण्डुरमेतत् दन्तताटकं मया गृहीतम् । मन्ये उद्यानलक्ष्म्याः श्रवणपाशात् प्रभ्रष्टमिति ।}

विदूषकः - ता मह देसु एदं, जेण दे किंपि अच्छरिअं दंसेमि । {तस्मान्मम देहोतत् । येन ते किमप्याक्षर्यं दर्शयामि।}

23. पदानि त्वगतार्थानि तदर्थगतये नराः । योजयन्ति पदैरन्यैस्तदुद्घात्यकमुच्यते ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/112, 113

24. See the text of *Līlāvati*, pp. 23, after the verse 14

25. यत्रान्यस्मिन् समावेश्य कार्यमन्यत् प्रसाध्यते । तच्चावलगितं नाम विशेष्यं नाट्ययोक्तृभिः ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/112, 113

(नेपथ्ये)

वेहासिअ ! सव्वं मए जाणिदं तुह्माणं कवटणाटअं । एदं वीळावदीए सहत्थळिहिअगाहासणा
दन्तताडङ्कं पमादणिहिणो तुह हत्थादो पब्भट्टं ति । ता गह दाव एदं, महाराअं च दंसेहि । पच्चा अवत्थाणु
अणुहोह । अहं गमिस्सम् । {वैहासिक ! सर्वं मया ज्ञातं युष्माकं कपटनाटकम् । एतल्लीलावत्या
स्वहस्तलिखितगाथासनाथं दन्तताटकं प्रमादनिधेस्तव हस्तात् प्रभ्रष्टमिति । तस्माद् गृहाण तावदेतत् । महारा
च दर्शय । पश्चादवस्थानुरूपमनुभवतम् । अहं गमिष्यामि²⁶ ।}

3. अवस्यन्दितम् (transferred significance) :

Avasyanditam (transferred significance) is where an auspicious or inauspicious meaning presented is interpreted otherwise by one's intelligence.²⁷ In the prologue *Natī*, on the request of *Sūtradhāra*, sings :

नटी - तह (गायति) -

गुरुअरविरहुक्कण्ठं सळिळहरो विहळटादअमहेळम् ।
मणरहघडणेण ळहुं आणंद(अ)इ मंदहुंकारो ॥७॥

{तथा - गुरुतरविरहोत्कण्ठां सलिलधरो विह्वलचातकमहेलाम् । ।
मनोरथघटनेन लघ्वानन्दयति मन्द्रहुक्कीरः ॥²⁸

This can be interpreted with the intelligence, that *Līlāvati*, who deeply loves king *Vīrapāla*, suffers separation, and finally, meeting her beloved king *Vīrapāla*, gets delected.

4. नालिका (enigmatic expression) :

Nālikā is an enigmatic speech in the form of laughing at others.²⁹

26. See the text of *Līlāvati*, before the verse No. 29

27. आक्षिप्तेर्थे तु कस्मिंश्चिच्छ्रुभाशुभसमुत्थिते । कौशलादुच्यतेऽन्योऽर्थस्तदवस्यन्दितं भवेत् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/

28. See the text of *Līlāvati*, the verse No. 7

29. हास्येनोपगतार्था प्रहेलिका नालिकेति विशेषः । नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/115

Here the statement of *Vidūṣaka* “अहं दुग्धसागरं उज्झित्वा कुतो लक्ष्मीरुच्छति ।”³⁰ (अथवा दुग्धसागरमुज्झित्वा कुतो लक्ष्मीरुच्छति ।)” is an enigmatic speech in the form of laughing at the love and association between *Virapāla* and *Līlāvati*.

5. असत्प्रलापः (incoherent talk)

Asatpralāpa or incoherent talk is another *vīthyaṅga*. We have an example for this in the scene where the *vidūṣaka*, on hearing about the serpent, imagines that he had already fallen into the tongue of the serpent³¹. Here is the example :

विदूषकः - (सभयं राजानमालिङ्गन्) भो ! वयस्स ! दुग्धविसहरजीहाजुअळन्तरपटिअं मं परित्ताआहि³²
{भो वयस्य ! दुग्धविषधरजिह्वायुगलान्तरपतितं मां परित्रायस्व ।}

6. वाक्केलिः (repartee)

एकद्विप्रतिवचना वाक्केलिः स्यात् प्रयोगेऽस्मिन् ।³³

Vākkeli (repartee) is where one engages in playful talk in the form of a few question and answer.

हंहो केळिमाळे ! कर्हिं पत्थिदासि । किं भणासि - पिअसहीए कज्जरहस्सं अन्तरेण अय्यं एव्व पेक्खिदुं ति । (सगर्व) को अण्णो मह महाबह्णस्स समसीसं उब्बहइ रहस्सचिन्ताअं । ता भण विस्सद्धम् । किं भणासि - अपि तुवं रहस्सं रक्खिदुं पारेसि ति । (सरोषमिव) आः अविस्सम्भसीळे ! भणाहि दाव । णहि बुदी एव्व खज्जइ सस्सं । किं भणासि - ता सुणाहि दाव । (अये लीलावत्याः प्रियसखी केलीमाला इत एवागच्छति । तदेनां पृच्छामि हंहो केलिमाले ! कुत्र प्रस्थितासि । किं भणासि ? प्रियसख्याः कार्यरहस्यमन्तरेणार्थमेव प्रेक्षितुमिति । कोऽन्यो मम महाब्राह्मणस्य समशीर्षमुद्बहति रहस्यचिन्तायाम् । तस्माद् भण विस्सब्धम् । किं भणासि ? अपि त्वं रहस्यं रक्खितुं पारयसीति ? आः अविश्रम्भशीले ! भण तावत् । नहि वृत्तिरेव खादयसि सस्यम्) ।³⁴

30. See the text of *Līlāvati*, after the verse No. 14.

31. मूर्खजनसन्निकर्षे हितमपि यत्र प्रभाषते विद्वान् ।

न च गृह्यतेऽस्य वचनं विज्ञेयोऽसावसत्प्रलापस्तु ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/116.

32. See the text of *Līlāvati*, after the verse No. 38.

33. नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/117.

34. See the text of *Līlāvati*, before the verse No. 11.

Here *Vidūṣaka* is engaged in playful talk in the form of a few questions and answer with *Kelimālā*; that is an example of वाक्केलि: or repartee according to dramaturgy.

7. प्रपञ्चः (exaggeration) :

Prapañca (exaggeration) is the trickling conversation resorting to falsehood between two person in order to achieve the goal of one giving a comic relief.³⁵ For example :

³⁶विदूषकः - (दृष्ट्वा) हन्त ! एसा दासीए धीदा देवीए पिअसही कंदळीआ एदं गहिअ वारंटे । {हन्त एषा दास्याः दुहिता देव्याः प्रियसखी कन्दलिकैतद् गृहीत्वा वाचयति ।} (उपसृत्य) कन्दलि किं एदं ? (कन्दलिके किमेतत् ?)

(नेपथ्ये)

वैहासिअ ! तुमं कंपि सिळोअं अज्झावइस्सं ता मह पादेसु पणामं करेहि । {वैहासिक ! त्वां कम्पि श्लोकमध्यापयिष्यामि । तस्मान्मम पादयोः प्रणामं कुरु ।}

विदूषकः - आ. कहं महाबहाणो दासीए पादेसु पणामं करेदि । अह कुदो एदं आसादिअम् । {अ. कथं महाब्राह्मणो दास्याः पादयोः प्रणामं करोति । अथ कुत एतदासादितम् ?}

(नेपथ्ये)

एत्थ उज्जाणे वम्पीअरन्धमुहट्टिअं सप्पणिम्मोअं विअ घणपण्णुरं एदं दन्तताडइकं मए गहीदं । मण्णे उज्जाणळच्छीए सवणपासादो पव्वट्ठं ति । {अत्रोद्याने वल्मीकरन्ध्रमुखस्थितं सर्पनिर्मोकमिव धनपाण्डुरमेतत् दन्तताटकं मया गृहीतम् । मन्ये उद्यानलक्ष्म्याः श्रवणपाशात् प्रप्रष्टमिति ।}

विदूषकः - ता मह देसु एदं, जेण दे किंपि अच्छरिअं दंसेमि । {तस्मान्मम देहोत्तत् । केत ते किमप्याश्चर्यं दर्शयामि ।}

35. यदसद्भूतं वचनं संस्रवयुक्तं द्वयोः परस्परतः ।

एकस्य चार्थहेतोः सहास्यजननः प्रपञ्चः स्यात् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/118

36. See the text of *Lilāvati*, after the verse No. 28

(नेपथ्ये)

वेहासिअ ! सव्वं मए जाणिदं तुह्माणं कवटणाटअं । एदं लीळावदीए सहत्थळिहिअगाहासणाहं
दन्तताडङ्कं पमादणिहिणो तुह हत्थादो पब्भट्टं ति । ता गह दाव एदं, महाराअं च दंसेहि । पच्चा अवत्थाणुस्वं
अणुहोह । अहं गमिस्सम् । {वैहासिक ! सर्वं मया ज्ञातं युष्माकं कपटनाटकम् । एतल्लीलावत्याः
स्वहस्तलिखितगाथासनाथं दन्ततताटकं प्रमादनिधेस्तव हस्तात् प्रभ्रष्टमिति । तस्माद् गृहाण तावदेतत् ।
महाराजं च दर्शय । पश्चादवस्थानुरूपमनुभवतम् । अहं गमिष्यामि ।}

विदूषकः - (ससान्त्वनम्) पसीअ कन्दळिए पसीअ । एक्कं मह अवरहं मरिसेहि । {प्रसीद कन्दलिके
। प्रसीद । एकं ममापराधं मर्षय ।}

Here the trickling conversation resorting to false hood between *Vidūṣaka* and maiden (*ākāśabhāṣitam*) in order to achieve the goal.

8. मृदवम् (softening)

Mṛdavam (softening) is the falsification of good qualities and praise of bad qualities³⁷ to the opposite effect.

राजा - (वाचयति)

सजळजळहरा वा उज्जळा विज्जुळा वा
सुरहिळमहुवाही केअईमारुओ वा ।
विरहिमहणकीळाकर्मठो वम्महो वा
सुहअ ! तुइ कए मं णामसेसं कुणन्ति ॥३६॥

{सजलजलधरा वोज्जला विद्युतो वा
सुरभिलमधुवाही केतकीमारुतो वा ।
विरहिमथनक्रीडाकर्मठो मन्मथो वा
सुभग ! तव कृते मां नामशेषां कुर्वन्ति ॥}

37. यत्कारणाद् गुणानां दोषीकरणं विवादकृतम् ।
दोषगुणीरणं वा तन्मृदवं नाम विज्ञेयम् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/119.

Here the beatific elements of rainy days, although appear pleasing to all, but become the cause of pain to the king Virapāla, that is the falsification of good qualities, may be treated as a dramatic technology मृदवम् (softening).

9. अधिबलम् (strengthening argument) :

Adhibalam (strengthening argument) is where two person are engaged in mutual conversation or argument and each finding arguments in support of their respective position.³⁸

(पुनर्नेपथ्ये)

कण्ठि दृढमत्सरेण मनसा जागर्ति यः प्रत्यहं

मित्रं तस्य बली कलिङ्गनृपतेस्ताम्राक्षनामासुरः ।

मायाकर्मणि लम्पटः प्रियसखीमात्रानुयात्रामसौ

कष्टं कर्षति कैशिके गतघृणो लीलावती लीलया ॥५५॥

विदूषकः - (सभयकम्पं) अविहा । अविहा । {अविघा अविघा ।}

(नेपथ्ये)

"तिष्ठ तिष्ठ पापासुर ! तिष्ठ ।

सुस्निग्धे पेलवालीकरजविरचिते केशपाशे कृशाङ्ग्या-

स्तत्रोदग्रं कराग्रं सपदि निदधतः कालदण्डोपनानम् ।

क्रूरेङ्गारतारे धनुषि कृतपदस्सायको मामकीन-

श्ण्डस्ते कण्ठपीठी मृदुतरकदलीकाण्डलावं लुनातु ॥५६॥

Here The King Virapāla's dialogue supports his arguments, when Līlavatī is caught by the demon Tāmrākṣa is an example of *Adhibalam* (strengthening argument).

38. परवचनमात्मनश्चोत्तरसमुद्भवं द्वयोर्यत्तु ।
अन्योन्यार्थविशेषकमधिबलमिति तद्वुधैर्विज्ञेयम् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/120

39. Līlavatī, verse No. 56

10. छलम् (misinterpretation)

Chalam (misinterpretation) is misconstruction of a sentence in order to deceive another or to provoke him.⁴⁰

⁴¹विदूषकः - आअङ्गुच्चाडणतंतरूहं

वहामि तिक्खाण वि पण्णआणम् ।

वेउंठपळ्ळङ्कमअं महाहिं

विद्दावएउं वि ण मे पआसो ॥४०॥

{आकर्षणोच्चाटनतन्त्ररूपं वहामि तीक्ष्णानामपि पन्नगानाम् ।

वैकुण्ठपर्यङ्कमयं महाहिं विद्रावयितुमपि न मे प्रयासः ॥}

(विचिन्त्य स्वगतम्) णमो बन्धुसिणेहस्स जस्स पहावेण एस बेहासिअबहणो इमं जुउच्चिअं वेसं गह्हाविओ । {नमो बन्धुस्नेहस्य यस्य प्रभावेणैष वैहासिकब्राह्मणः इमं जुगुप्सितं वेषं गृहीतः ।} (पुरोऽवलोक्य) एदं अन्तेवुरदुवारं जाव पविसामि । {इदमन्तःपुरद्वारं यावत्प्रविशामि ।} (प्रविश्य) भो भद्रसिद्धी णाम जह्गळ्ळिअग्गेसरो ह्मि एत्थ सम्पत्तो । {भो भद्रसिद्धिर्नाम जाङ्गलिकाग्गेसरोऽस्म्यत्र सम्प्राप्तः ।}

11. त्रिगतम् (tripled or manifold) :

Trigatam (tripled or manifold) is where more than one meaning is assigned derisively or otherwise to the similarity or word in sound and expression and which is supported by reasoning.⁴² The application of this dramatic technique can be seen here as under :

राअहंस ! मह पडकइणीए

दंसिऊण खणमप्पविळासम् ।

सम्पअं पुण घणुक्कळ्ळिअं मे

केवलं कुणसि जुत्तमिदं ते ॥२७॥

40. अन्यार्थमेव वाक्यं छलमभिसन्धानहास्यरोषकरम् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/120.

41. *Lilāvati*, verse No. 40.

42. श्रुतिसारूप्याद्यस्मिन् बहवोऽर्था युक्तिभिर्नियुज्यन्ते ।

यद्वास्वमहास्यं वा तत् त्रिगतं नाम विज्ञेयम् ॥ नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/121.

{राजहंस मम पङ्कजिन्या दर्शयित्वा क्षणमात्मविलासम् ।
साम्प्रतं पुनर्घनोत्कलिकां मे केवलं करोषि युक्तमिदं ते ॥}

Here the king is abused of forgetting someone beloved with who once there was a close affinity of love and affection. this suggested meaning is derived from the directly implied meaning, i.e. the *Rajahamsa* (The king swan and *pankajinī* (the lotus). This type of expression is called *Trigata* (tripled or manifold) that is a constituent part of *Vīthī*.

12. व्याहारः (talk)

Vyāhāra (talk) is the direct expression with a view to evoking some laughter.⁴³ Example :

विदूषकः - (सभयं राजानमालिङ्गन्) भो ! वयस्स । दुद्रुविसहरजीहाजुअळन्तरपटिअं मं परित्ताआहि
{भो वयस्य ! दुद्रुविषधरजिद्वायुगलान्तपतितं मां परित्रायस्व ।}

राजा - सखे ! मा भैषीः । नु नरेन्द्रोऽहं तव समीपे । तदेहान्तः पुरमेव प्रविशावः ।

Here even in the mighty association of the Hero *Virapāla GandamVidūṣaka* gets trembled and expresses fear directly without any hesitation that ultimately constitutes a significant example of *Vyāhāra*.

13. गण्डम् (junction or knot)

Gandam (junction or knot) is an unexpected combination of words consisting in putting one speech immediately after another, so as to be syntactically connected.⁴⁵ For example :

राजा - (स्वगतम्) हन्त ! तदेव बीजं तदेवाङ्कुरः । (प्रकाशम्) देवि ! कृतमिमं दालक
गम्भीरमुपालम्भ्य ।

43. प्रत्यक्षवृत्तिरुक्तो व्याहारो हास्यलेशार्थः । नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/122

44. *Līlāvati*, after the verse No. 37

45. बहुवचनाक्षेपकृतं गण्डं प्रवदन्ति तत्त्वज्ञाः । नाट्यशास्त्रम्, 20/123

प्रहरसि मदिराक्षि ! प्रेमभाजं किमेवं
 जनमिममतिकोपक्रूरतारैरपाङ्गैः ।
 तव सुमुखि ! शपेऽहं पादपङ्केरुहाभ्यां
 यदि भवति मदीयं जातु चेतोऽन्यदास्थम् ॥४६॥

(आकाशे)

कस्स एत्थ कोवो । सिविणो मं बाहेइ । ता अहं गमिस्सं । {कस्यात्र कोपः । स्वप्नो मां बाधते । तस्मादहं गमिष्यामि ।}

Here King Virapāla mentions the anger of Līlāvati in the verse जनमिममतिकोपक्रूरतारैरपाङ्गैः that is immediately followed by the speech of Līlāvati (in *Ākāśa-bhāṣitam*) कस्स एत्थ कोवो {कस्यात्र कोपः ।}. This type of unexpected combination of words consisting in putting one speech immediately after another, leading to syntactical connection, produces the example of *Gaṇḍam* (junction or knot).

c) Employment of *rasas* :

It is quite evidently established that to suit to the principal element in the theme of the play, that is the love affair between Līlāvati and Virapāla, *Śṛṅgāra rasa* has been employed predominantly, and this is extensively treated throughout the play. But in keeping in view with the rule 'सृशेदपि रसान्तरम्' the author has also depicted as subordinate *rasas adbhūta* in the stratagem of Siddhimatī, *bhayānaka* in the cobra incident, *vīra* in the Tāmrākṣa episode and *hāsya* in the *Vidūṣaka's* role.

Without *vipralambha śṛṅgāra*, *Sambhoga śṛṅgāra* can not be nourished sufficiently, as it is said that

न विना विप्रलम्भेन सम्भोगः पुष्टिमश्रुते ।

कषायिते हि वस्त्रादौ भूयान् रागो विवर्धते ॥

Keeping this in view *vipralambha śṛṅgāra* has been extensively employed in this play. It is *vipralambha śṛṅgāra* as we find the hero and heroine pining for each other throughout the play. The lovelorn condition of Līlāvati is very well brought out by her friend Kelimālā:

श्रयति गरलच्छायं भूयः पयोधरमण्डली-
 विवरगलितानिन्दोःपादानसौ विरलानपि ।
 कथमपि पुरोवातानेतान् विकस्वरकेतकी-
 परिमलभृतो दावासेवं सखी मम सेवते ॥⁴⁶

The *vipralambha śṛṅgāra* as brought out in the character study of the king *Vīrapāla* and *Līlāvati*, go to prove the ability of the dramatist in depicting this *rasa* delicately yet poignantly.

Vidūṣaka the only character other than the king, is presented on the stage. With the presence of *Vidūṣaka* there is bound to be scope for *hāsya* and the play does have humour in good measure. But it never hinders the progress of the main *rasa*, because *hāsya* is a supporting *rasa* to *śṛṅgāra*. On the other hand, it supports the principal *rasa* in the process of *praśamana* whenever the *śṛṅgāra* reaches its peak. In fact, the main *rasa* should never be taken to the breaking point. It should be delineated in the pattern of a wave, taken to great heights and immediately brought down to normal level with the help of a secondary *rasa*. The *hāsya* in the play helps in this process. There is humour in the boasting of the *vidūṣaka*, his disorderly reference to the number of the Vedas and the *Purāṇas*, his foolhardiness in losing the signet of *Līlāvati* and in his appearance as the disguised snake charmer. When the queen's attendant recovers the signet, carelessly dropped by the *vidūṣaka*, she says sarcastically "I think it is got dropped from the ear of the presiding deity of the gardens".⁴⁷ When the queen offers the hand of *Līlāvati* to the king, the later asks for the opinion of the *vidūṣaka* who makes a cryptic remark by saying "Who will forsake the food when invited?".⁴⁸ The dramatist has, in fact, exhibited a very dignified sense of humor throughout the play.

46. *Ibid.*, p. 12

47. मन्ये उद्यानलक्ष्म्याः श्रवणपाशात् प्रभ्रष्टमिति । *Ibid.*, p. 14

48. आमन्त्रितः को मिष्टभोजनं परिहरति । *Ibid.*, p. 27

Adbhuta is also employed in the play sufficiently. When *vidūṣaka* thinks of seeking the help of the *yoginī*, the wonderful dream witnessed by the queen, in which she has seen Lord *Śiva* appearing before her and the description of it evokes *adbhuta*.

दृष्टः स्वप्ने फणिवलयिना पाणिना पाणिनालं
मन्दं मृद्रत्रचलदुहितुर्बालचन्द्रावतंसः ।
पादन्यासप्रचलनबलद्भोगिनिह्वासवात-
क्षुभ्यद्गङ्गासलिलमुखरीभूतकोटीरभारः ॥⁴⁹

The *adbhuta* is revealed in the serpent bite scene as well. We have an instance of *vīra* in the act of the king's destruction of the demon which is described vividly in the following verse.

तिष्ठ तिष्ठ पापासुर ! तिष्ठ ।
सुस्रिग्धे पेलवालीकरजविरचिते केशपाशे कृशाङ्ग्या-
स्तत्रोदग्रं कराग्रं सपदि निदधतः कालदण्डोपमानम् ।
क्रूक्रेङ्कारतारे धनुषि कृतपदस्सायको मामकीन-
श्चण्डस्ते कण्ठपीठीं मृदुतरकदलीकाण्डलावं लुनातु ॥५६॥

The element of *bhayānaka* in the description of the demon is found. The appearance of the terrible serpent is equally frightful that nourishes *bhayānaka* :

उत्तानीकृतभोगमण्डलचलज्जिह्वाकरालाकृति-
र्द्रष्टाकोटिपरिस्रवद्विषकणश्रेणिनिषिक्तावनिः ।
वेत्रोदशितपाणिभिर्भयवशान्मुक्तान्तिको वेत्रिभिः
कष्टं कोऽपि महोरगः स्वयमसावन्तःपुरं गाहते ॥३७॥

d) The delineation of characters in the play

Rāmapānivāda portrays his characters as real and as vividly as Kālidāsa. He develops his characters from the realities of the society. His art of characterization is based on social justice and natural law. He constructs the characters on the foundation of reality, but not on that of idealism. He never tries to impose fundamentalism over realism.

49. Ibid., p. 50

• **Lilāvati**

The play takes its title from one of its central characters, a young woman Lilāvati. The theme of the whole play is centered around the love affair; between Lilāvati and Virapāla, the king of the Kuntala. To befit the nature of the play the poet portrays Lilāvati, the heroine of the play, in such a way that she remains incognito for the audience throughout the play, still the poet delineates her character so skillfully that he out of his dramatic art, transforms the obscurity and incomprehensibility in to lucidity and clarity, that one can feel her presence by the force of the dramatic action and the references made about her by the other characters. She is described as one possessing extraordinary beauty.⁵⁰ She is the daughter of the king of Karṇātā. But she, being forced by the circumstances, is exiled from his father's own state to that of Kuntala. She is in love with the king Virapāla to whom she sends a love letter along with the signet of her ear ring. She shows considerable ingenuity in designing the letter. At the outset it appears as though she is addressing the royal swan. But the term 'rājā' refers to the king and 'paṅkaja' (lotus) to her self, indirectly.⁵¹

But subsequently she expresses her love and affection to the king Virapāla more explicitly in her love letter. She says : Be it the cloud dotted with water drops, be it the lightening, be it the breeze carrying the fragrance of *ketakī* flower, be it the cupid who tortures the love lorn women, O' noble one, on account of you, (they) just compel me to remain with name only (without physical existence).⁵²

50. असाधारणरूपलावण्या कन्यका लीलावती कुतोऽत्रानीता, *Vidūṣaka.*, mentions after the verse 13

51. राजहंस ! मह पङ्कङ्गीणं दसिंऊण खणमप्पविलासम् ।

सम्पअं पुण धणुक्कळिअं मे केवलं कुणसि जुत्तमिदं ते ॥२७॥ Meaning "O Royal Swan, having 'shown your splendour' for just a moment, you desert me to suffer like this. Is it proper?"

52. सजळजळहरा वा उज्जळा विज्जुळा वा सुरहिळमहुवाही केअईमारुओ वा ।

विरहिमहणकीळाकर्मठो वम्महो वा सुहअ ! तुइ कए मं णामसेसं कुणन्ति ॥३६॥

The solicitousness of the lovelorn condition of Līlāvati as described by Kelimālā is pitiable; i.e. "She does not care for a bath or food. She is spending sleepless nights. She does not mind about the daily routine, nor does she listen to the words of friends. She lies on the couch always undergoing the pangs of separation".⁵³

Her nobility and patience ultimately results in uniting with her most beloved, the abode of love, the king Virapāla.

• Virapāla

Virapāla, the king of the Kuntala is the hero of the play. He is a replica of such kings seen in plays like *Mālvikāgnimitra* and *Ratnāvalī*, a *dakṣiṇa nāyaka*. He is deeply in love with Līlāvati, the princess of the state Karnāta. His love for her is revealed in his anxious enquiry about her. He is reminded of her lovely charms. He asks *Vidūṣaka* :

अपि खलु कुशलं मे नेत्रयोरायतानामपि च जघनभारे दूरविस्तारभाजाम् ।
कुचसरसिजयुग्मे चोन्नतानां घनानां दशनवसनबिम्बे चारुणानामसूनाम् ॥२२॥

When he learns that the queen, becoming suspicious has kept Līlāvati under special security, he loses all hopes of meeting her. He pines for her and explains his condition to his friend *Vidūṣaka* and seeks his help in his love affair. The breeze carrying the fragrance of full blown jasmine flower, adds to his misery. He says :

गहिरपओहरत्थणिए मअमेउरमोरमिहुणणिहुवणए ।
कहवि गमेइ वराई तुह पणयाळंबणा दिअहे ॥२३॥

His address to the cupid can reveal his lovelorn conditions explicitly :

बाणान् संहर पशबाण ! मधुपज्यावल्लरीसंहितान्
मुशामुं च शरासमैक्षवमहो व्यर्थस्तवायं श्रमः ।
केकाभिश्च शिखण्डिनामविरलश्च्योतत्परागोत्करी-
मालत्याः प्रसवैश्च केवलममी दूयामहे यद्वयम् ॥२७॥

53. न स्नाने न च भोजने न शयने धत्ते मनागादरं नादत्ते करणीयवस्तुघटनायत्तं सखीनां वचः ।
सर्वहृत्कं विरहव्य पल्लवमयीं शय्यां सदा सेवते कष्टं सम्प्रति वीरपालविरहाल्लीलावती दूयते ॥२१॥

He describes his beloved Līlāvati as one of the best creation of the love God cupid in the following verse :

लोकत्रयप्रथितमोहनवस्तुसार्थैः
 स्पृष्टं स्वयं भगवता मकरध्वजेन ।
 तस्याः सखे ! निरुपमं वदनारविन्दं
 भूयः कदाचिदपि नाम विलोकयेयम् ॥४८॥

He feels that the queen's anger about his love affair is fully justified, that he expresses saying :

किमपि चपलं जानत्या मे सुखेन सखीमुखा-
 दरुणिमगुणो देव्या नाद्यापि मुञ्चति लोचने ।
 कुचकलशयोः कोपोदीर्णो न शाम्यति वेपथु-
 र्गततलगलद्वाष्पो रुन्धतरां परुषाक्षरम् ॥२५॥

His love for the queen is equally strong as for Līlāvati. He never ignores the queen at all. When he comes to know that the queen is bitten by the serpent, he swoons immediately unable to bear the intensity of the calamity. when he gets up, he laments that it is useless to live without her.

दष्टा चेदणकभुजङ्गमेन देवी
 कष्टं भो विफलामिदं हि जीवितं मे ।
 कर्णाटक्षितिपतिकन्यकानुरक्तं
 हे चेतो जहिहि शतं मनोरथानाम् ॥३९॥

After the revival of queen he feels relieved and says :

यत्ते बालशिरीषनूतनदलस्पर्धालु मुग्धं वपुः
 कष्टं दष्टमभूत्करालगरलज्वालेन कालाहिना ।
 तेनानेन जनेन सुन्दरि ! चिरं मूर्च्छायितं सांप्रतं
 शान्ते तत्र विषोष्मणि श्वसितमित्येतन्महत्कौतुकम् ॥४४॥

He has great regard for his bosom friend, *vidūṣaka*. He seeks his help in all his activities, especially in the love affair. When the king wants to

to the queen, the *vidūṣaka* hesitates to join them saying “यतो द्वयोस्तृतीयत्वं
भवति ।” But the king says “अभिन्नो हि भवान्मत्तः ।” meaning : ‘you
are not different from me’. He praises the endeavor of his friend *vidūṣaka*
that resulted in achieving success in the following verse :

सखे ! भवत्प्रयत्नेन फलितमिदानीम् । पश्य-

दोष्यमिव स नक्रचक्रडटिलं वारान्निधिं सन्तरेत्

पद्ममेव स लङ्घयेदपगतालम्बं नभोमण्डलम् ।

दुस्साधाखिलकर्मसाधनविधौ पाण्डित्यमत्यूर्जितं

विभ्राणा सुहृदां कटाक्षलहरी जागर्ति यस्योदये ॥५९॥

He possesses high standards of heroic qualities; as he gets into action
immediately on hearing that *Līlāvati* is abducted. He chases the demon and
kills him, showing extraordinary valour. He shows great dignity when the
queen herself arranges his marriage with *Līlāvati*.

He narrates the reality of the society, that substantiates his intellectual
and philosophical outlook, as under :

गोष्ठी सा विरला न यत्र घटले सत्ता पुरोभागिनां

नारी सा खलु दुर्लभा न कुसृतिश्लिष्टं यदीयं मनः ।

दुष्प्रापं च तदम्बु तीरजरजोराजिर्न यद्दूषयेद्

दुस्साधश्च सुखं तदाविलयते दुःखानुवृत्तिर्न यत् ॥५८॥

Meaning : “It is very rare to find an assembly where the noble alone
will be present. It is mixed with jealous people also. It is difficult to see
the river whose water does not carry the slush and dirt from the banks.
Likewise, it is difficult to find happiness that is unmixed with misery in
this world.”

The character of *Vīrapāla*, is portrayed in such a way that shows a
balance between realism and idealism. The dramatist never ignores either
of these

ism and idealism. Because it is told :

अनौचित्यादृते नान्यद्रसभङ्गस्य कारणम् ।
औचित्योपनिबन्धस्तु रसस्योपनिषत्परा ॥

To maintain appropriateness (औचित्य), the poet, out of his imagination, has a right to change the real to ideal, for which he (the poet) is described to be the creator (प्रजापति) of his poetic creation.

अपारे काव्यसंसारे कविरेकः प्रजापतिः ।
यथास्मै रोचते विश्वं तथासौ परिवर्तते ॥

● **Kalāvati :**

Kalāvati is the queen and first wife of the king Vīrapāla. She is portrayed in a two-dimensional attitude. On the one hand, she is possessive, as every woman is and would not like to share her husband's love with other lady, but at the same time she is prepared to make any sacrifice for the welfare of her husband. Knowing well the weakness of her husband for pretty women, she zealously guards Līlāvati from the eyes of the king; that is natural tendency of a woman. She becomes angry when she comes to know of about the love affair between Vīrapāla and Līlāvati. But due to the effect of the magical powers of the *yoginī*, she changes her mind and offers *Līlāvati* to her husband since that would fetch him the title of "supreme monarch" as per the astrological predictions.

● **The Vidūṣaka :**

Viśvanātha defines *Vidūṣaka* :

कुसुमवसन्ताद्यभिधः कर्मवपुर्वेशभाषाद्यैः ।
हास्यकरः कलहरतिर्विदूषकः स्यात् स्वकर्मज्ञ ॥⁵⁴

Vidūṣaka, often named as Kusuma, Vasanta and like, a character, is witty and humorous by his action, physique and speech etc. He is fond of futile argument.

54. Visvanatha, *Sāhityadarpaṇa*, 3/42

In this play he is called by the name Vaihāsika. True to his name (a hilarious person) he is full of wit, humour and satire. He is referred to as *narmasaciva* (a love counsellor) of the king.

While boasting own credentials he, often due to his improbable statements, becomes an object of jest and ridiculousness.

यथेष्टमष्टादशवेदवेदी चतुष्पुराणोदधिपारगामी ।

वैहासिको नाम महीसुरोऽहम् न पूजितः कस्य घटयामि कार्यम् ॥१०॥

I am a scholar of eighteen Vedas and I have crossed the ocean of four Purāṇas. I am a Brahmin called Vaihāsika. I, if not worshiped, whose job shall accomplish?

By this statement he only parades his own ignorance. Actually the Vedas are only four in number and the Purāṇas are eighteen. He says that he can put in extraordinary effort in his pursuits.⁵⁵ But in reality he is very careless in his activities. He drops the signet ear ring given by Līlāvātī to be passed on to the king. He says “उत्तरिज्जदिद्वद्वं पि तं दन्ताडङ्कं पद्मद्वम्”.⁵⁶ He is rightly ridiculed as *pramādanidhi*.⁵⁷ (a heap of errors).

He always tries to support his friend king Vīrapāla and accomplish his tasks even with deceitful means. Kelimālā, the friend of the heroine says “वैहासिअ ! को उण दे कवडणाडअं ण जाणादि ।”⁵⁸ (Who is not aware of your deceitful tricks?). Kandalikā, the queen’s attendant is also of the same opinion. She says “सव्वं मए जाणिदं तुह्माणं कवटणाटअं ।”⁵⁹ (I know everything about your deceitful tricks).

He also boasts himself that he is a man of strong mind : “दिद्वहिअओ खु वैहासिअबहणो”⁶⁰ But just on hearing that a serpent has entered the harem,

55. को एत्थ संदेहो, जर्हि असाहारणप्पआसो वैहासिअबहणो, *Ibid*, text after the verse 48

56. *Ibid*, text after the verse 27

57. पमादणिहिणो तुह हत्थादो पद्मद्वं ति, *Ibid*, text before the verse 29

58. *Ibid*, text after the verse 14

59. *Ibid*, text before the verse 29

60. *Ibid*, text after the verse 14

he raises hue and cry saying that “भो वयस्य ! दुष्टविषधरजिह्वायुगलान्तरपतितं मां परित्रायस्व ।”⁶¹ (O friend ! Save me, who has fallen into the twin tongues of the serpent).

For all his foolhardiness, he is resourceful. In order to help the king in his love affair, he seeks the help of *yoginī* and this step proves to be the turning point in the play. then again, coming in the disguise of a snake charmer, he pretends to save the queen and thereby wins her favor. He boasts that he can cure anybody of any kind of serpent bite by his pronouncement of the *tāntric mantras*.

आअट्टुणुच्चाडणतंतरूहं

वहामि तिक्खाण वि पण्णआणम् ।

वेउंठपळळड्कमअं महाहिं

विदावएउं वि ण मे पआसो ॥४०॥

He is so dexterously deceitful that even the king is not in a position to identify him.

अये को नु खल्वेषः-

आवीतमलिनवसनो दण्डाग्रप्रथितसर्पपेटिकः ।

अविरलशङ्खाभरणो मुखविलिखितरोचनातिलकः ॥⁶²

Alas ! Who is this, being clad in a dirty cloth, holding a serpent-box through a club, wearing a garland of conches and sporting a mark of *tilaka* on his fore head !

His cryptic remarks sound appropriate to the situation. He advises the king to go ahead with his love affair unmindful of the possible protest from the queen. He says “Who will refrain from taking a pearl for the fear of breaking the nacre?” (भो वअस्स होदु एव्वम् । को सिप्पिभञ्जणभएण मुत्तावळिं उज्झदि ?)⁶³ It is no wonder that the king is very fond of him. He cannot remain without

61. *Ibid*, text after the verse 37

62. *Ibid*, verse 42

63. *Ibid*, text before the verse 26

him even for a moment. when the king reaches a breaking point out of love-lorn condition, he diverts his attention to something else and saves him.

e) Concept of Beauty in Nature

The beauty of the nature reached such a degree of perfection that it does not escape from our imagination. Furthermore, such portrayal of the beauty of nature has most of its richness in the figures he employed.

Let us open our eyes to magnificent sights of the dance of the peacocks and strain our ears to the melody of thundering, mixed with the songs, sung by the bees at par with the coming of the rains :

गम्भीरनीरदमृदङ्गरवाभिरामं
भृङ्गाङ्गनामधुरगीतकलासनाथम् ।
विद्युत्प्रदिपकलिते विपिनान्तरङ्गे
नृतोत्सवं वितनुते ननु नीलकण्ठः ॥१६॥

Deep in the forests with light provided by the lightning, the peacocks render a dance recital to the tune of sweet music provided by the female bees and the percussion provided by the water laden clouds.

Even the *vidūṣaka*, who generally does not pay much attention to the beauties of nature, is captivated by the charm of the season and sings in praise of cupid in a beautiful verse studded with *atiśayokti* (hyperbole) and *virodha* (apparent incongruity).

बाणा जस्स विसट्टचूदकळिआ जीआ अ भिंगावळी
मित्तं वा ससळंच्छणो रणचमूथट्टो तरट्टीअणो ।
सोअं संकरणेत्तपावअपुरोडासो वि पंचाउहो
धीरणं वि मणाइ णेइ ण खणा हंहो दसं केरिसिम् ॥१५॥

The cupid's arrows are the mango sprouts. The bow-string, the swarm of bees; his friend is the moon; his soldiers are beautiful young women; thus the cupid, though roasted in the fire emanating from the eyes of Lord Śiva, still torments the minds of even the brave ones.

f) **Employment of Figures of speech or *alaṅkārayojanā* :**

The Figures of speech employed in *Līlāvātīvīthī* are spontaneous derived consequently nurturing the principal sentiment or *āṅgīrasa* in the play. It may be the *śabdālaṅkāra* or *arthālaṅkāra* that is subordinate broaching itself to the process of heightening the principal sentiment in the play. The dramatist, by his emotional suffusion and out of poetic genius, he effortlessly employed these that could suggest the predominant emotion. The alliterations or *anuprāsas* occurring in the text have a spontaneity that appear to be the natural gift of the poetic talent. There are some evidences, cited here to the context :

एते नूतनकेतकीदलगलन्माध्वीकधाराकिराः

स्निग्धन्दीवरनीलनीरदघटासम्पर्कशीतोत्कराः ।

मन्दान्दोलितहूणवारतरुणीवेणीकलापस्रजः

पौरस्त्या मरुतो न कस्य रभसादुत्कण्ठयेयुर्मनः ॥१८॥ (also No. 22)

Not only in the poems, but in the prose also the spontaneity of *anuprāsas* can be seen. For example in the *vidūṣaka's* statement; cursing the serpent :

“मा सा काळरूवकाळकाकोअरकराळकाकोळजळणिहिम्मि पडसु । {मा मा कालरूपकालकाकोदरकरालकाकोलजलनिधौ पततु ।}”⁶⁴

Arthālaṅkāras also contribute to promote the poetic beauty to such an extent that those sufficiently suggest the predominant theme of the play. अतिशयोक्ति (hyperbole), अनुप्रासः (alliteration), अप्रस्तुतप्रशंसा (indirect description) उत्प्रेक्षा (poetic fancy), उदात्त (exalted), उपमा (simile), काव्यलिङ्ग (poetic reason), निदर्शना (illustration), परिणाम (transformation), यमक (assonance), रूपक (metaphor), वक्रोक्ति (indirect denotation), विरोधाभास (apparent contradiction), संकर (commixture), संसृष्टि (collocation of figures), समासोक्ति (modal metaphor) and स्वभावोक्ति (natural description) are the *arthālaṅkāras* found through this masterpiece of the *Rāmapāṇivāda*, that reveal his extraordinary poetic genius. For instance, the beauty of simile or *upamā* is seen in the following dialogue :

64. *Ibid*, Before the verse 38.

“अत्रोद्याने वल्मीकरन्ध्रमुखस्थितं सर्पनिर्मोकमिव घनपाण्डुरमेतत् दन्तताटङ्कं मया गृहीतम् ।”⁶⁵

And also in the following verse :

एते नूतनकेतकीदलगलन्माध्वीकधाराकिराः

स्निग्धन्दीवरनीलनीरदघटासम्पर्कशीतोत्कराः ।

मन्दान्दोलितहूणवारतरुणीवेणीकलापस्रजः

पौरस्त्या मरुतो न कस्य रभसादुत्कण्ठयेयुर्मनः ॥१८॥

The ecstasy of suggestiveness can be experienced in the embellishment of *samāsokti* (modal metaphor) in the verse here :

राअहंस ! मह पडकङ्गीए

दंसिऊण खणमप्पविळासम् ।

सम्पअं पुण घणुक्कळिअं मे

केवलं कुणसि जुत्तमिदं ते ॥२७॥

Similarly, the rapture of *kāvyaṅga* (poetic reason) and *utprekṣā* (poetic fancy) could also be experience here :

दिगङ्गनासूढपयोधरासु यन्

न्यलायि कान्तेन मयूखमालिना ।

निमज्ज्यते वारिणि लज्जमानया

सरोरुहिण्या किमनेन हेतुना ॥३३॥

i) The style of narration / expression

The witty saying of the dramatist is his unique style of expression that presents the dialogues more interestingly and creates fun and fancy in the minds of readers / spectators. Some examples of his style of expression are cited here :

65. *Ibid*, Before the verse 29.

- णहि बुदी एव्व खज्जइ सस्सं ।⁶⁶ (नहि वृतिरेव कादयति सस्यम् ।) The fence or hedge never eats the crops itself. Generally a fence is made to protect the crops around the land and the same fence never eats the crops. With this statement the *vidūṣaka* justifies that he is capable of protecting a secret and that he will not cause harm to the king himself since he is close associate.
- अहव दुद्धसाअरं उज्झिय कुदो लच्छी उगच्छइ ।⁶⁷ (अथवा दुग्धसागरमुज्झित्वा कुतो लक्ष्मीरुच्छति ।)

Where else will Lakṣmī stay disregarding the milky ocean. In this statement the *vidūṣaka* justifies the nobility of birth of Līlāvati.

- अमहिज्जमाणं दही ण णवणीदं मुञ्चेदि ।⁶⁸ (अमथ्यमानं दधि न नवनीतं मुञ्चति ।) The unchurned curds will not produce butter. Here the *vidūṣaka* says that it requires great efforts to get Līlāvati released from the clutches of the queen.
- को सिप्पिभज्जणभरण मुत्तावळिं उज्झादि ।⁶⁹ (कः शुक्तिभज्जनभयेन मुक्तावलिमुञ्चति ।) Who will leave the pearl for the fear of breaking the shell ? In this quotation the intention of the *vidūṣaka* is that the king should not mind about the queen's anger while seeking the love of Līlāvati.
- को दुद्धसाणापाणसमए आरणाळं चिन्तेदि ।⁷⁰ (को दुग्धस्नानपानसमये आरणाळं चिन्तयति ।) Who will think of soar gruel while getting a chance to bathe and drink in the milky ocean ? In this dialogue the *vidūṣaka* encourages the king to read the love letter without worrying about the queen.)
- कस्स उण अत्तणो जीविअसंसए परकेरए अहिणिवेसो ।⁷¹ (कस्य पुनरात्मनो जीवितसंशये परकीयेऽभिनिवेशः ।) How will one think after others when one's own life is under threat. *Vidūṣaka* tries to conceal the truth of his disguise of the serpent by expressing fear with these words.

66. Before the verse 11

67. After the verse 14

68. Before the verse 15

69. Before the verse 26

70. After the verse 29

71. After the verse 47.

- दुवेणं तीअत्तणं जुउच्छिदं होइ । ⁷² (द्वयोस्तृतीयत्वं जुगुप्सितं भवति ।) With two persons, if one more is added, it does not augur well. Here there is a belief that if a group of three persons sets out together for a work it will spell doom and the secrecy will fall in exposure.
- कुदो पंकङ्णि विणा राअहंसस्स णिव्वुदी । ⁷³ (कुतः पङ्कजनीं विना राजहंसस्य निर्वृतिः ।) Where is the relief for the royal swan without resorting to the lotus ? Here Yoginī orders Kalāvati to approve the wedding of the king with Līlāvati that is the only wish of the Vīrapāla.
- आमन्तिदो को मिट्ठभोजणं परिच्चेदि । (आमन्त्रितः को मिष्टभोजन परिहरति ।) After Yoginī orders Kalāvati to approve the wedding of the king with Līlāvati then Vidūṣaka being asked by Vīrapāla what to do, expresses his consent with these words.

Conclusion

This study reveals that *Vīthī* is given less importance by the dramatists of Sanskrit among other forms of drama. There might be more in number among the composed *Vīthīs*, but a meager account of *Vīthī* literature is available now. It appears that some other compositions of *Vīthī* might have been lost, undiscovered or unpublished. The innovative, tender and meticulous nature of this type might have restrained the poets to compose in this form that lead to its scantiness, Never the less these are the few specimens of this type breathing '*Līlāvati*', the magnum opus of Rāmapānivāda, due to its rich poetic beauty, innovative dramatic art, lucid style of language and expressions, magnificent plot etc. is treated as one of the best among these. Although having a single act, a *Vīthī* satisfactorily pleases the connoisseurs with the tenderly employed *Śṛṅgāra rasa*. *Līlāvati Vīthī* of Rāmapānivāda embodies all those dramatic features, due to which, it not only supercedes all of this type but other types of theatrical forms also.

72. After the verse 49.

73. After the verse 52.

Bibliography

1. *Bharata, Nāṭyaśāstram*, Kāvyaṃālā Edition, Published by Bharatiya Vidya Prakashan, 1983.
2. *Dhanañjaya, Daśarūpaka*, with the commentary *Avaloka* by Dhanika, and the subcommentary *Laghuṭīkā*, by Bhaṭṭantaṣiṃha, Published by Adyar Library and Research Centre, Madras, 1969.
3. *Rāmapāñivāda, Lilāvati*, Published by The University Manuscripts Library, University of Travancore, Trivandrum, Printed by the Superintendent Government Press in 1948.
4. *Viśvanātha Kavirāja, Sāhityadarpaṇa*, withh *samīkṣātmaka bhūmikā, Hindī-anuvāda-vyākhyātmaka tippanī sahita*, Published by Nirupaṇa Vidyālaṅkāra, Merāṭha : Sāhitya Bhaṇḍāra, 1974-1978.

LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS

SUDHIRA PANDA

Institute of Mathematics and Applications, Andharua, Bhubaneswar - 751003, M: 9438675845,
E-mail: sudhira@iopb.res.in

T. GANESAN

Department of Indology, French Institute of Pondicherry, Pondicherry, M: 8870607728,
E-mail: ganesan@ifpindia.org

S. BHUVANESHWARI

Doshi Etopia -II, Block 4C-201, 3rd Link Panchayat Road, Perungudi, Chennai 600096;
M: 9940059778, E-mail: nissangabs@gmail.com.

NIRANJANA JENA

Deptt. of Sanskrit, Pali & Prakrit, Visva-Bharati Central University, Santiniketan, West Bengal,
M: 9434569621, E-mail: santinjena@gmail.com

SATYA VRAT VARMA

7/34, Purani Abadi; Near Namdev Flour Mills; Sri Ganganagar-335001

ANIL NARAYANAN

School of Linguistics & Literary Studies, ChinmyaVishwavidyapeeth, Ernakulam, M: 09746009987,
E-mail: anilnrynn@yahoo.com

N. C. KAR

Department of Indian Studies, Hankuk University of Foreign Studies, South Korea; M: 9811665171;
E-mail: neckara@gmail.com

KANIKA GUPTA

Visual Studies, School of Arts and Aesthetics, Jawaharlal Nehru University, Delhi,
E-mail: kanika.arthistory@gmail.com

SUGYAN KUMAR MAHANTY

Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, (Deemed University), Vedavyas Campus, Balahar, Dist.: Kangra (HP) -
177108, M: 9625627362, E-mail: sugyan2003@yahoo.co.in

KUSH P. DEPALA

School of Oriental and African Studies, London. E-mail: kushdepala@gmail.com

SWETA PRAJAPATI

Oriental Institute, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Opp. Palace Gate, Palace Road,
Vadodara-390001 M: 9898472669, E-mail: sprajapati22@yahoo.com

SHARMILA BAGCHI

Oriental Institute, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara-390001 (Guj.),
M: 9426947941 E-mail: milibagchi2003@yahoo.com

RABINDRA KUMAR PANDA

Dept. of Sanskrit, Pali & Prakrit, Faculty of Arts, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda,
Vadodara-390020, M: 9974262038, E-mail: panda_rabindra@rediffmail.com

VIPUL PATEL

Oriental Institute, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Opp. Palace Gate, Palace Road,
Vadodara-390001, M: 9898656871, E-mail: vipul.1063@gmail.com.

Regd. No. 15007/57

Published by Dr. Sweta Prajapati, I/c. Director, Oriental Institute, on behalf of The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara - 390 001 (India)

Printed by Jatln H. Somani, Manager, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda Press (Sadhana Press), Near Palace Gate, Palace Road, Vadodara - 390 001

Issued - February 2020

MSUP-4509-250+10-2-20